

1 **Title: Energy saving potential of a hybrid HVAC system with a desiccant wheel activated at**
2 **low temperatures and an indirect evaporative cooler in handling air in buildings with high**
3 **latent loads**

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9 **Abstract**

10 Air handling in buildings with high latent loads usually requires a high-energy cost to satisfy the
11 user's thermal comfort needs. Hybrid systems composed of desiccant wheels, DW, and indirect
12 evaporative coolers, IEC, could be an alternative to direct expansion conventional systems, DX
13 systems. The main objective of this work was to determine the annual energy consumption of a
14 hybrid system with a DW activated at low temperatures and an IEC, DW-IEC system, compared
15 to a DX system to serve air in a small building with high latent loads, such as spas. Several annual
16 energy simulations for 6 climate zones were performed, analysing electric energy consumption,
17 seasonal mean coefficient of performance, SCOP, and energy consumption per unit of
18 dehumidified water, E_{cons} , of each system. The simulations were based on experimentally
19 validated models.

20 The annual energy consumption of the DW-IEC system was lower than that of the DX system for
21 the 6 climate zones, achieving significant energy savings, up to 46.8%. These energy savings
22 resulted in better SCOP values for the DW-IEC system. Therefore, the proposed DW-IEC system
23 has high potential to reduce energy costs, achieving the user's thermal comfort.

24 **Keywords:** hybrid system; desiccant wheel; indirect evaporative cooler; high latent loads; climate
25 zones

Nomenclature

b	estimated parameter
C	capacity rate of air [$\text{kJ h}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
c_p	specific heat of air [$\text{kJ kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
CO	condenser
COP	coefficient of performance
DW	desiccant wheel
DX	direct expansion
EA	exhaust air
E_{cons}	energy consumption per unit of dehumidified water [Wh kg^{-1}]
EIR	electrical input ratio
EV	evaporator
IEC	indirect evaporative cooler
h	air specific enthalpy [kJ kg^{-1}]
HC	heating coil
k	number of parameters
MRC	moisture removal capacity [kg h^{-1}]
\dot{m}	mass air flow rate [kg h^{-1}]
\dot{M}_{pool}	evaporated water flow of the pool [kg h^{-1}]
N_p	number of people
OA	outdoor air
PLF	partial load factor
P	static pressure [mmca]
\dot{Q}	heat transfer [kW]
RA	return air
S	area [m^2]
SCOP	seasonal mean coefficient of performance
SHE	sensible heat exchanger
T	dry bulb temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
T_{wb}	wet bulb temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
UA	overall heat transfer coefficient [$\text{kJ h}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
v	air velocity [m s^{-1}]
\dot{V}	volumetric air flow rate [$\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$]
\dot{V}_w	water flow rate of indirect evaporative cooler [l h^{-1}]
\dot{W}	electric power consumption [kW]
X	input variable
\hat{Y}	estimated output value

Greek letters

Δ	increase
ε	effectiveness
ρ	density [kg m^{-3}]
Σ	sum
ω	humidity ratio [g kg^{-1}]
Ω	specific mass air flow rate [$\text{kg s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-3}$]

Subscripts

a	air
c	condenser
e	evaporator

HC	heating coil
i	inlet
IA	indoor air
lat	latent
N	nominal
o	outlet
OA	outdoor air
p	process air; primary air
s	secondary air
r	regeneration air
sen	sensible
t	total
T	temperature
w	water
<i>Superscripts</i>	
'	dimensionless value

26 **1 Introduction**

27 Air handling in buildings with high latent loads usually requires a high-energy cost to satisfy the
 28 user’s thermal comfort needs. Indoor swimming pools or spas are some examples of this type of
 29 buildings, which have high internal latent gains, due to the great amount of evaporated water from
 30 the wet areas [1]. Excessive air humidity can cause discomfort for the occupants and problems
 31 related to the indoor air quality of the building due to fungus and rot [2]. Therefore, an air handling
 32 system is required to control the indoor moisture content, while keeping a low energy
 33 consumption.

34 A traditional method of dehumidifying rooms with high latent loads is to introduce a certain air
 35 flow rate from outside, this method can only be used when the outdoor humidity ratio is lower
 36 than the indoor humidity. In this method [3], the air flow rate required to dehumidify the building
 37 was very high. The recommended air change rates per hour values were shown to vary between
 38 4 h^{-1} and 7 h^{-1} in order to obtain thermal comfort [3]. This dehumidification method could cause
 39 discomfort to the occupants in small rooms with high latent loads, such as spas, due to the high
 40 air change rates per hour values.

41 Another method widely used in dehumidifying air is that of conventional dehumidification
 42 systems based on direct expansion units, DX system, which operates according to the vapor-

43 compression cycle. DX systems reduce the air temperature below its dew point in order to
44 condense water. An increase in the cooling power of the DX system usually produces an increase
45 in its desiccant capacity. However, DX systems have a cooling capacity limit when the required
46 dew-point temperature is very low, close to 0 °C, the freezing point of water. Moreover, the outlet
47 air temperature of DX systems is usually very low, so a post-heating of air flow is necessary,
48 before being supplied to the building. Several DX systems have been studied for indoor swimming
49 pools [4,5], where high energy consumption values were required to dehumidify and heat the air
50 steam. A comparative study between a DX system and an open absorption system to handle air
51 in an indoor swimming pool, was carried out by other authors [6], obtaining significant energy
52 savings with the open absorption system. These studies show the need to search for new HVAC
53 systems in buildings with high latent loads.

54 Previous studies on energy saving in spas with small volumes and high latent loads have been
55 carried out [7–9]. However, these works focused on the hot water system of swimming pools.

56 Desiccant dehumidification systems present an alternative solution to DX systems. Desiccant
57 dehumidification systems adsorb water from the air in contact with an area of low vapour pressure
58 at the surface of the desiccant [10]. One type of desiccant dehumidification system widely used
59 is the desiccant wheel, DW, [11,12]. The most influential parameter on the desiccant capacity of
60 a DW is the regeneration temperature [13,14]. Usually, DWs are thermally activated at high
61 temperatures, from 60 °C to 120 °C [15,16], although other studies also showed acceptable DW
62 performance when their regeneration temperatures were below 60 °C [17]. The main disadvantage
63 of DWs is the high outlet process air temperatures [18]. This heat is generated by the adsorption
64 process of the DW, which is delivered from the regeneration section to the process section.
65 Therefore, a cooling system is needed to lower the process air temperature before being supplied.
66 Cooling systems based on evaporators of a DX system are usually combined with a DW [19,20],
67 but these systems normally require a high energy consumption [21]. Another cooling system that
68 is usually combined with DWs is the evaporative cooler. There are two types: the direct
69 evaporative cooler and the indirect evaporative cooler. The indirect evaporative cooler, IEC,

70 system is one of the most promising technologies in reducing the air temperature because of its
71 higher energy saving capacity compared to DX systems [22]. The IEC system requires two
72 separate air flows to operate. The primary air flow which is cooled and supplied to the building
73 without increasing its humidity ratio and the secondary air flow which is humidified with water
74 supplied to the outside [23].

75 Many studies about IEC integrated into a desiccant system have been carried out [24–26]. An
76 experimental study on a hybrid system composed of a DW and an IEC was carried out for several
77 summer days in Italy [27]. This system reduced the electrical consumption significantly compared
78 to one composed of a DW and two cooling coils fed by a conventional vapour compression chiller.
79 A numerical simulation study on desiccant units presented a comparative analysis of three
80 different systems with a DW and an IEC [28]. The results of this study indicated that all of them
81 were able to obtain satisfactory supply air temperatures, even when the DW was regenerated at
82 low temperature. Other numerical studies analysed the behaviour of a DW combined with an IEC
83 system [29–32]. They were mainly based on the hybrid system performance optimization under
84 different steady state air conditions, always using the IEC system to cool the output air stream of
85 the DW.

86 Based on the limitations in the air treatment with conventional HVAC systems within the
87 framework of air conditioning in buildings with small volume and high latent loads, such as spas,
88 it would be interesting to analyse the energy saving potential and the annual behaviour of a
89 novelty hybrid system based on DW and IEC in handling air in buildings with high latent loads
90 and low supply air flow rates, decoupling sensible and latent loads by using low temperature
91 energy sources. The main objective of this work was to determine the annual energy consumption
92 of a hybrid HVAC system composed of a DW activated at low temperatures and an IEC,
93 compared to a DX system composed of a direct expansion unit for a small building with high
94 latent loads. Hence, several annual energy simulations for different climate zones were carried
95 out. Electric energy consumption, \dot{W} , seasonal mean coefficient of performance, SCOP, and
96 energy consumption per unit of dehumidified water, E_{cons} , of each system were analysed.

97 2 Methodology

98 2.1 System description

99 A criterion commonly used by manufacturers to select dehumidification units, is their moisture
100 removal capacity, MRC [5]. In this study, this criterion was used. The same nominal MRC value
101 for both systems was considered, 15.2 kg h^{-1} . The selected DX system was specifically designed
102 to maintain indoor conditions in swimming pools and other high latent loads buildings, such as
103 spas [33]. Both systems studied were not equipped with any humidifier element, since they were
104 designed to handle very humid indoor air.

105 2.1.1 DX system

106 A numerical model of a DX system was created in order to compare its operational behaviour
107 with the proposed DW-IEC system. The DX system was composed of an air-mixing box, a vapor-
108 compression cycle and a heating coil, HC, see Fig. 1. The HC was fed by a constant water flow,
109 which was heated using an air-water heat pump. The evaporator, EV, and the condenser, CO, of
110 the vapor-compression cycle were installed in a parallel arrangement.

111 Air handling by the DX system is described below. Firstly, the outdoor air stream was mixed with
112 the return air stream. Secondly, the mixed air stream was dehumidified and cooled by the
113 evaporator, EV. Finally, the air stream was heated by the HC until the supply air temperature
114 equalled the set point temperature. The supply air humidity ratio was controlled with the EV and
115 the supply air temperature was controlled with the HC. The outdoor air flow rate of this system
116 was $1600 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$, and the total air flow rate handled and supplied by the DX system was 3680 m^3
117 h^{-1} . The condenser, CO, of the direct expansion refrigeration unit handled 100% outdoor air, 3680
118 $\text{m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$.

119

120

Fig. 1. Schematic of the DX system.

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2.1.2 DW-IEC system

122

An alternative DW-IEC system was proposed in this piece of work in order to maintain the

123

required indoor conditions in buildings with high latent loads. A schematic of the DW-IEC system

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is shown in Fig. 2. It is composed of a DW to handle latent heat loads in the room, and an IEC

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and a heating coil, HC2, to handle sensible heat loads. The DW was activated by means of a

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heating coil, HC1. Alternatively, the IEC was used as a sensible heat exchanger, SHE, recovering

127

sensible heat from the return air stream, when it was necessary to heat the process air stream. In

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addition, two air boxes were integrated into the system to increase the desiccant and cooling

129

capacity of the DW and the IEC, respectively. Both boxes have two air inlet dampers and one

130

outlet. Depending on outdoor air conditions, the exhaust air stream is the outside, OA, air or return

131 air, RA, as shown in Fig. 2. A constant air flow rate of $1600 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ was considered for the three
 132 air streams. The outdoor air flow rate of this system was equal to that of the DX system.
 133 Furthermore, this study was performed for relatively low regeneration air temperatures (40–60
 134 °C), which can be obtained using a commercial heat pump.

135

136

Fig. 2. Schematic of the DW-IEC system.

137

2.1.2.1 System operation modes

138

Two independent main control loops were considered in the DW-IEC system. The first one was
 139 an indoor air humidity control loop and the second one an indoor air temperature control loop. A
 140 diagram of the control logic of the DW-IEC system is represented in Fig. 3. The air humidity
 141 control loop was divided into two specific modes of operation, Mode 1-H and 2-H. This loop

142 modulated the water flow rate of the regeneration heating coil, HC1, activated the rotation of the
 143 DW and set the position of the dampers in the DW and IEC boxes. The air temperature control
 144 loop was divided into three specific modes of operation, Mode 1-T, 2-T and 3-T. This loop
 145 modulated the water flow rate of the IEC and the post-heating coil, HC2. These modes of
 146 operation are described below.

147

148

Fig. 3. DW-IEC system control logic diagram.

149 • **Air humidity control**

150 The operating mode of the selected humidity control was based on the outdoor air humidity ratio,
 151 ω_{OA} . The DW-IEC system did not dehumidify when the outdoor air humidity was lower than the
 152 set point air humidity. Mode 1-H was activated, see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. For this operating mode,
 153 the DW, HC1 and Fan3 elements were disabled, and as a result the supply air humidity ratio was
 154 equal to the outdoor air humidity ratio. On the contrary, the DW-IEC system dehumidified when
 155 the outdoor air humidity was higher than the set point air humidity, and Mode 2-H was activated.

156 For this control mode, the system dehumidified the outdoor air until the outlet process air
157 humidity ratio of the DW, $\omega_{p,o}$, was equal to or lower than the set point humidity. The DW, HC1
158 and Fan3 elements were activated and the dampers of the two air boxes were set to the correct
159 position, see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The outdoor air, OA, passed through DW damper and the return
160 air, RA, passed through IEC damper when the outdoor air temperature was higher than the set
161 point air temperature. On the contrary, the outdoor air, OA, passed through IEC damper and the
162 return air, RA, passed through DW damper.

163 • **Air temperature control**

164 The operating mode of the selected temperature control was based on the DW outlet process air
165 temperature, $T_{p,o}$. Mode 1-T was activated when $T_{p,o}$ was higher than the set point air temperature,
166 see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The IEC system was activated until the set point temperature of the process
167 air stream was achieved. The process air stream was heated when $T_{p,o}$ of the DW was lower than
168 the set point air temperature. The outlet process air stream of the DW can be heated by the sensible
169 heat exchanger, SHE. The IEC was only used as SHE when the rotation of the DW was disabled
170 and the secondary air stream was return air. In this situation, no water was evaporated in the SHE.
171 Then, the air temperature was measured again at the output of the IEC unit, see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.
172 The primary air stream of the IEC was supplied to the building when $T_{p,o}$ was higher than the set
173 point air temperature, and the HC2 was off, Mode 2-T. However, HC2 was activated when $T_{p,o}$
174 was lower than the set point air temperature and the air stream was heated until the supply air
175 temperature was equal to the set point temperature, Mode 3-T.

176 **2.2 Building model – Spa**

177 Both HVAC systems were designed to serve air in a building with high latent loads. A building
178 model was designed to simulate the thermal behaviour of a spa. This was modelled and simulated
179 using TRNSYS package tool [34]. The building consisted of a single surface of 64 m² and a height
180 of 3.9 m, where a wall, south orientation, and the roof were exterior. The characteristics of the
181 building are summarized in Table 1.

182 The building was composed of a swimming pool of 32 m² and a daily maximum number of 8
 183 people in the pool. The evaporated water flow rate from the pool was calculated using Eq. (1),
 184 according to that established in [5]. Where S is the pool area, ω_w is the saturated air humidity ratio
 185 at the pool water temperature, ω_{IA} is the indoor air humidity ratio and Np is the number of people.
 186 Other internal energy gains due to people and lighting were considered, as shown in Table 1.

$$\dot{M}_{pool} = S \cdot \left(16 + 133 \cdot \frac{Np}{S} \right) \cdot (\omega_w - \omega_{IA}) + 0.1 \cdot Np \quad (1)$$

187 Based on the Spanish regulations on thermal installations in buildings [35], the indoor air
 188 temperature set for swimming pools should be between 1 and 2 °C above the pool water
 189 temperature, with a maximum of 30 °C, and the indoor relative humidity should be maintained
 190 below 65 %. In this paper, the indoor conditions were set at 27 °C for the air temperature and 60
 191 % for the relative humidity. The building was simulated for a daily operating schedule from 09:00
 192 am to 24:00 pm.

193 Table 1. Characteristics of the building.

Building	Floor area	64 m ²
	Height	3.9 m
	Exterior wall area	31.2 m ²
	Exterior roof area	64 m ²
	Indoor air temperature	27 °C
	Indoor relative humidity	60 %
Pool	Area	32 m ²
	Water temperature	25 °C
U-value	Exterior wall	0.339 W m ⁻² K ⁻¹
	Roof	0.313 W m ⁻² K ⁻¹
Heat gain	Pool	Latent: 6662 W ($\dot{M}_{pool}=9.6$ kg h ⁻¹)
	Lighting	55 W m ⁻² (50 % convective part)
	People	8 persons
		Sensible: 75 W/person Latent: 75 W/person
Daily schedule	09:00 am to 24:00 pm	

194 2.3 Components modelling

195 The components that compose the proposed DW-IEC system and the DX system, were modelled
 196 as described below. Each of the component models was combined and integrated into TRNSYS
 197 [34]. The models of the DW, the IEC, the refrigeration vapour compression unit, the heat pump

198 and the fans were validated experimentally. These models were fitted by first, second and third
 199 order polynomial equations, expressed by Eqs. (2)-(4), respectively, where \hat{Y} is the estimated
 200 output value, X are input variables, b_i , b_{ii} , b_{iii} and b_{ij} are the estimated parameters of linear,
 201 quadratic, cubic and the second-order terms, respectively, and b_0 is the average response in the
 202 model.

$$\hat{Y} = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i \cdot X_i \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{Y} = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i \cdot X_i + \sum_{i=1}^k b_{ii} \cdot X_i^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{Y} = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i \cdot X_i + \sum_{i=1}^k b_{ii} \cdot X_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{k=1} b_{iii} \cdot X_i^3 \quad (4)$$

203 **2.3.1 Desiccant wheel model**

204 The desiccant wheel model behaviour was studied in a previous paper [17]. This model was based
 205 on the statistical technique of design of experiments. The model was adjusted to obtain the outlet
 206 process air temperature and humidity ratio in the DW, $T_{p,o}$ and $\omega_{p,o}$, especially for low
 207 regeneration temperature activated systems. The input variables of the model were the inlet
 208 process air temperature and humidity ratio, $T_{p,i}$ and $\omega_{p,i}$, the inlet regeneration air temperature and
 209 humidity ratio, $T_{r,i}$ and $\omega_{r,i}$, and the process specific mass air flow rate, $\Omega_{p,i}$. In this study, the
 210 process and regeneration specific mass air flow rates were always maintained constant, 21.51 kg
 211 $s^{-1} m^{-3}$. The relationship between the output and input variables was examined using second order
 212 polynomial equations, expressed by Eq. (3). The corresponding estimated parameters of the DW
 213 model are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Estimated parameters of the DW empirical model.

b_x	X_i	$T_{p,o} \times 10^3$ [°C]	$\omega_{p,o} \times 10^3$ [g kg ⁻¹]	b_x	X_i	$T_{p,o} \times 10^3$ [°C]	$\omega_{p,o} \times 10^3$ [g kg ⁻¹]
b_0	-	-6736.67	-15366.80	b_{11}	$\omega_{p,i}^2$	-17.23	16.76
b_1	$T_{p,i}$	72.10	1277.57	b_{12}	$\omega_{p,i} \cdot T_{r,i}$	-1.49	-2.23
b_2	$\omega_{p,i}$	772.28	-785.18	b_{13}	$\omega_{p,i} \cdot \omega_{r,i}$	5.65	16.84
b_3	$T_{r,i}$	410.38	1310.33	b_{14}	$\omega_{p,i} \cdot \Omega_{p,i}$	20.50	-6.79
b_4	$\omega_{r,i}$	224.17	-916.88	b_{15}	$T_{r,i}^2$	-5.09	-11.90
b_5	$\Omega_{p,i}$	357.36	-94.71	b_{16}	$T_{r,i} \cdot \omega_{r,i}$	7.31	-10.40
b_6	$T_{p,i}^2$	16.58	-28.38	b_{17}	$T_{r,i} \cdot \Omega_{p,i}$	6.71	-3.50
b_7	$T_{p,i} \cdot \omega_{p,i}$	-14.35	29.84	b_{18}	$\omega_{r,i}^2$	-9.72	24.41
b_8	$T_{p,i} \cdot T_{r,i}$	7.35	-10.61	b_{19}	$\omega_{r,i} \cdot \Omega_{p,i}$	-5.49	11.88
b_9	$T_{p,i} \cdot \omega_{r,i}$	-12.93	6.35	b_{20}	$\Omega_{p,i}^2$	-12.17	-9.44
b_{10}	$T_{p,i} \cdot \Omega_{p,i}$	-8.71	5.89	-	-	-	-

215 2.3.1 Indirect evaporative cooler model

216 The model used to study the behaviour of the IEC was studied in a previous paper [36] and was
217 based on the statistical technique of design of experiments, as well as the model used for the DW.
218 The IEC empirical model was able to accurately predict the outlet primary air temperature, $T_{p,o}$,
219 the outlet secondary air temperature, $T_{s,o}$, and the outlet secondary air humidity ratio of the system,
220 $\omega_{s,o}$, under different operating conditions. The input variables were the inlet primary air
221 temperature, $T_{p,i}$, the inlet secondary air temperature, $T_{s,i}$, the inlet secondary air humidity ratio,
222 $\omega_{s,i}$, the secondary air velocity, v_s , and the water flow rate, \dot{V}_w . The relationship between the input
223 and output variables was expressed by Eq. (2). The corresponding estimated parameters of the
224 IEC model are shown in Table 3.

225 Table 3. Estimated parameters of the IEC empirical model.

b_x	X_i	$T_{p,o} \times 10^3$ [°C]	$T_{s,o} \times 10^3$ [°C]	$\omega_{s,o} \times 10^3$ [g kg ⁻¹]	b_x	X_i	$T_{p,o} \times 10^3$ [°C]	$T_{s,o} \times 10^3$ [°C]	$\omega_{s,o} \times 10^3$ [g kg ⁻¹]
b_0	-	-1313.76	3801.74	-379.62	b_8	$T_{p,i} \cdot v_s$	-15.66	-25.34	-35.06
b_1	$T_{p,i}$	322.41	500.49	183.23	b_9	$T_{p,i} \cdot \dot{V}_w$	-1.23	-2.02	1.12
b_2	$T_{s,i}$	364.07	191.57	135.71	b_{10}	$T_{s,i} \cdot \omega_{s,i}$	-8.45	-5.85	3.32
b_3	$\omega_{s,i}$	766.52	455.43	313.29	b_{11}	$T_{s,i} \cdot v_s$	26.11	42.55	-6.63
b_4	v_s	-467.09	-1199.63	755.41	b_{12}	$T_{s,i} \cdot \dot{V}_w$	-2.11	-1.54	0.92
b_5	\dot{V}_w	41.87	20.99	3.33	b_{13}	$\omega_{s,i} \cdot v_s$	12.58	19.45	33.91
b_6	$T_{p,i} \cdot T_{s,i}$	0.42	0.60	0.19	b_{14}	$\omega_{s,i} \cdot \dot{V}_w$	2.87	3.37	-2.39
b_7	$T_{p,i} \cdot \omega_{s,i}$	-5.09	-3.93	6.28	b_{15}	$v_s \cdot \dot{V}_w$	-0.94	3.94	-4.54

226 The IEC was used as a SHE when it was necessary to heat the process air stream and not to cool
227 it, as was mentioned previously. For this reason, a cross flow sensible heat exchanger with both
228 hot and cold sides unmixed, was modelled. The physical design characteristics of SHE were
229 similar to those of the IEC [36]. The effectiveness of the SHE at each time step was calculated by

230 Eq. (5), where UA is the overall heat transfer coefficient of the exchanger, C_p is the capacity rate
 231 of air on primary side ($C_p = \dot{m}_p \cdot c_{p,p}$) and C_s is the capacity rate of air on secondary side ($C_s =$
 232 $\dot{m}_s \cdot c_{p,s}$). In this work, the effectiveness of the SHE was calculated for a fixed value of UA , given
 233 the inlet temperatures and air flow rates. The UA value of the cross-flow heat exchanger was
 234 measured experimentally for a wide range of input conditions, obtaining an average value of 1440
 235 $\text{kJ h}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1 - \exp\left(-\frac{UA}{C_s} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{C_s}{C_p}\right)\right)}{1 + \frac{C_s}{C_p}} \quad (5)$$

236 **2.3.2 Refrigeration vapour compression model**

237 The considered refrigeration vapour compression unit of the DX system was specially designed
 238 to dehumidify indoor swimming pools and other dehumidification applications. This unit was
 239 modelled using experimental data available from the manufacturer [33]. The unit works for
 240 balanced air flow rates in both coils, with a value of $3680 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$.

241 A simplified experimental model based on correlations was obtained to study its behaviour [37].

242 The relationship between the output and input variables was expressed by second order
 243 polynomial equations, as shown in Eq. (3). The input variables of this model were the inlet
 244 evaporator dry bulb air temperature, $T_{e,i}$, the inlet evaporator wet bulb air temperature, $T_{wb,e,i}$, the
 245 inlet condenser dry bulb air temperature, $T_{c,i}$, and the volumetric air flow rate ratio, $\dot{V}' = \dot{V}/\dot{V}_N$.

246 The output variables were calculated using the following ratios: evaporator total heat transfer ratio

247 $\dot{Q}'_{e,t} = \dot{Q}_{e,t}/\dot{Q}_{e,t,N}$; evaporator sensible heat transfer ratio $\dot{Q}'_{e,sen} = \dot{Q}_{e,sen}/\dot{Q}_{e,sen,N}$; condenser

248 total heat transfer ratio $\dot{Q}'_{c,t} = \dot{Q}_{c,t}/\dot{Q}_{c,t,N}$; electric power consumption ratio $\dot{W}' = \dot{W}/\dot{W}_N$.

249 Where $\dot{Q}_{e,t}$ is the evaporator total heat transfer, $\dot{Q}_{e,sen}$ is the evaporator sensible heat transfer,

250 $\dot{Q}_{c,t}$ is the condenser total heat transfer and \dot{W} is the electric power consumption of the

251 compressor. The estimated parameters of the output variables are shown in Table 4. The nominal

252 characteristics of the vapour compression system obtained experimentally by the manufacturer

253 were used, see Table 5.

Table 4. Estimated parameters of the refrigeration vapour compression model.

b_x	X_i	$\dot{Q}'_{e,t}$ $\times 10^3$	$\dot{Q}'_{e,sen}$ $\times 10^3$	$\dot{Q}'_{c,t}$ $\times 10^3$	\dot{W}' $\times 10^3$	b_x	X_i	$\dot{Q}'_{e,t}$ $\times 10^3$	$\dot{Q}'_{e,sen}$ $\times 10^3$	$\dot{Q}'_{c,t}$ $\times 10^3$	\dot{W}' $\times 10^3$
b_0	-	145.20	202.46	264.37	622.12	b_8	\dot{V}'^2	-185.21	-249.68	-89.82	221.34
b_1	$T_{e,i}$	-1.79	33.88	-1.70	-1.00	b_9	$T_{e,i} \cdot T_{c,i}$	0.08	-0.28	0.09	0.09
b_2	$T_{c,i}$	8.45	8.93	7.82	7.34	b_{10}	$T_{e,i} \cdot T_{wb,e,i}$	-0.65	2.32	-0.56	-0.29
b_3	$T_{wb,e,i}$	17.71	-35.46	16.36	11.82	b_{11}	$T_{e,i} \cdot \dot{V}'$	3.55	57.59	2.77	0.18
b_4	\dot{V}'	475.27	610.50	280.22	-345.74	b_{12}	$T_{c,i} \cdot T_{wb,e,i}$	-0.34	0.46	-0.23	0.14
b_5	$T_{e,i}^2$	0.20	-0.95	0.18	0.09	b_{13}	$T_{c,i} \cdot \dot{V}'$	-0.29	-2.39	-1.24	-4.92
b_6	$T_{c,i}^2$	-0.24	-0.29	-0.12	0.27	b_{14}	$T_{wb,e,i} \cdot \dot{V}'$	3.97	-49.65	0.17	-11.94
b_7	$T_{wb,e,i}^2$	0.75	-1.81	0.66	0.39	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 5. Nominal parameters of the refrigeration vapour compression system.

Parameters	Value	
$\dot{Q}_{e,t,N}$	23.06	[kW]
$\dot{Q}_{e,sen,N}$	13.00	[kW]
$\dot{Q}_{c,t,N}$	30.32	[kW]
\dot{W}_N	7.53	[kW]
\dot{V}_N	4600	[m ³ h ⁻¹]

2.3.3 Heating coil with heat pump model

The heating coils of both systems studied, Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, were fed by a constant water flow,

which was heated by an air-water heat pump. The thermal power exchanged by the heating coil

was obtained by Eq. (6).

$$\dot{Q}_{HC} = \dot{V}_{a,i} \cdot \rho_{a,i} \cdot (h_{a,o} - h_{a,i}) \quad (6)$$

The selected air-water heat pump covered all the required sensible heat. This heat pump is fitted

with a scroll inverter compressor. The technical characteristics of the heat pump were: a nominal

heating capacity of 28.1 kW, a nominal electric power consumption 9.6 kW and a nominal COP

of 2.93 [33]. In order to obtain the electric power consumption of the heat pump, the simplified

experimental model obtained by the manufacturer was used [33]. The output variable of the model

was the heating electrical input ratio, EIR, which is the inverse of COP. The estimate EIR value

was calculated from Eq. (7), where EIR_N is its nominal value, EIR_T is a second order polynomial

equation based on the outdoor air temperature and outlet water temperature, as shown in Eq. (3),

and EIR_{PLF} is a third order polynomial based on the partial load factor, expressed by Eq. (4). The

estimated parameters of the estimate EIR value are shown in Table 6.

$$EIR = EIR_N \cdot EIR_T \cdot EIR_{PLF} \quad (7)$$

270

Table 6. Estimated parameters of the air-water heat pump model.

b_x	X_i	$EIR_T \times 10^3$	b_x	X_i	$EIR_{PLF} \times 10^3$
b_0	-	805.57	b_0	-	30.39
b_1	$T_{w,o}$	-4.20	b_1	PLF	1518.51
b_2	$T_{w,o}^2$	0.11	b_2	PLF ²	-1323.27
b_3	T_{OA}	-5.68	b_3	PLF ³	774.38
b_4	T_{OA}^2	0.11	-	-	-
b_5	$T_{w,o} \cdot T_{OA}$	-0.15	-	-	-

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2.3.4 Filter

272

Filters were characterized by a constant pressure drop in the air circuit. Several filters with F8 or

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G4 protection were considered, as shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The pressure drop of these filters

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are shown in Table 7. However, the increase of their pressure drop due to dust accumulation was

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not considered.

276

2.3.5 Fan model

277

The fans were sized to maintain the design air flow rate given the estimated system pressure drop.

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The air pressure drop of each component is shown in Table 7. The fans were modelled using

279

manufacturer data from Sodeca QuickFan software [38]. Three centrifugal fans were selected for

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the DX system and another three for the DW-IEC system, as shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The

281

return and exhaust fans of the DX systems were the same. These fans were also the same for the

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DW-IEC systems, but different from those of the DX system. The estimated parameters of the fan

283

models are shown in Table 8, where the output variables were static pressure, P , and electric

284

power consumption of the fans, \dot{W} . The relationship between the output and input variables was

285

expressed by second order polynomials, according to Eq. (3).

286

Table 7. Pressure drop of each component for the systems analysed.

Component	Pressure drop [Pa]
Desiccant wheel (process side)	350
Desiccant wheel (regeneration side)	380
Indirect evaporative cooler	146
Evaporator	40
Condenser	27
Heating coil	35
Air box with dampers	40
Filter (G4 protection)	60
Filter (F8 protection)	100
Air duct	40

Table 8. Estimated parameters of the fan models.

		DX system				DW-IEC system			
		Fan1		Fan2 and Fan3		Fan1		Fan2 and Fan3	
b_x	X_i	$P \times 10^3$ [mmca]	$\dot{W} \times 10^3$ [kW]						
b_0	-	35478.6	339.9	8824.7	162.2	191371	463.03	76510.9	194.7
b_1	\dot{V}	11.653	0.057	14.669	0.039	77.617	0.522	- 4.768	0.192
b_2	\dot{V}^2	0.004	-	- 0.004	-	-0.077	-	- 0.005	-

288

2.4 Climate zones

289

The performance of the DX and DW-IEC systems under several climatic conditions was evaluated

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according to ASHRAE climate classification [39]. This classification consists of 8 climate zones,

291

depending on the cooling degrees-day and heating degrees-day. In this study, both systems were

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simulated for the climate zones 1 to 6, from very hot to cold. Climate zones 7 and 8, very cold

293

and subarctic, respectively, were not used in this study because they are very dry, and therefore,

294

do not require a dehumidification system. The simulations were performed using the Meteonorm

295

weather data library [40]. One city from each of the 6 selected climate zones was chosen, see

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Table 9. A world map with the 6 selected cities is shown in Fig. 4, where the colour scale

297

represents the different climate zones and subzones around the world.

298

Table 9. Selected cities from each of the climate zone defined by ASHRAE.

Climate zone ^a	City	Thermal criteria ^b [°C]
1	Singapore	5000 < cooling degree-day
2	Taipei	3500 < cooling degree-day ≤ 5000
3	Tunis	cooling degree-day ≤ 2500 and heating degrees-day ≤ 2000
4	Barcelona	cooling degree-day ≤ 2500 and heating degrees-day ≤ 3000
5	Budapest	3000 < heating degrees-day ≤ 4000
6	Ottawa	4000 < heating degrees-day ≤ 5000

^a 1- Very hot, 2- hot, 3- warm, 4- mixed, 5- cool, 6- cold

^b $T_{base} = 10^\circ\text{C}$ for cooling degree-day; $T_{base} = 18^\circ\text{C}$ for heating degrees-day

299

300

Fig. 4. World representation of the different climate zones with the selected cities.

301 **2.5 Energy simulation**

302 Several detailed energy simulations were carried out with the assumption that both HVAC
303 systems served a spa with high latent loads. All the energy simulations were carried out with the
304 TRNSYS 17 software [34], using a time step of 15 minutes. The simulations were performed for
305 the selected six climate zones throughout the whole year.

306 The HVAC systems were evaluated according to the following parameters: electric power
307 consumption, \dot{W} , sensible and latent energy delivered, \dot{Q}_{sen} and \dot{Q}_{lat} , respectively, the seasonal
308 mean coefficient of performance, SCOP, expressed by Eq. (8), and the energy consumption per
309 unit of dehumidified water, E_{cons} , expressed by Eq. (9). The latter was calculated from the \dot{W} and
310 MRC parameters of the HVAC system, only when it was in dehumidification mode, i.e. when air
311 dehumidification was demanded by the system.

$$SCOP = \frac{\int (\dot{Q}_{sen} + \dot{Q}_{lat}) dt}{\int \dot{W} dt} \quad (8)$$

$$E_{cons} = \frac{\int \dot{W} dt}{\int MRC dt} \quad (9)$$

312 **3 Results and analysis**

313 The energy analysis of the simulations is presented in daily, monthly and annual analysis to
314 correctly understand the behaviour of both HVAC systems.

315 **3.1 Daily behaviour analysis**

316 The daily analysis was performed for the climatic conditions of Barcelona. A typical winter day,
317 January 10th, and a typical summer day, July 10th, were selected.

318 **3.1.1 Daily behaviour of the DX system**

319 The thermal behaviour and energy consumption of the DX system for a typical winter day and a
320 typical summer day are represented in Fig. 5. Regarding the winter day, in the first process of the
321 DX system, the outdoor air stream was mixed with return air stream, increasing its temperature
322 and humidity, see Fig. 5a. Nevertheless, this humidity was lower than the set point air humidity,
323 therefore the dehumidification mode was not activated and the air stream was not handled by the

324 EV. The mixing air stream was heated by the HC until the set point temperature value was
 325 achieved, and finally supplied to the building. The energy consumption values of the compressor
 326 and Fan 3 were equal to zero, as air dehumidification was not required, see Fig. 5b. The energy
 327 consumption of the HC was reduced when the outdoor temperature increased and the partial load
 328 factor of the heat pump decreased. Regarding the summer day, the mixing process also raised the
 329 humidity, therefore it was necessary to activate the dehumidification mode in order to reduce it,
 330 see Fig. 5c. The mixing air stream was dehumidified and cooled by the EV until the set point
 331 humidity was achieved. Then, the dry air flow was heated by the HC and supplied to the building.
 332 In this case study, the compressor consumed a significant amount of energy, as the latent energy
 333 required by the EV was high, Fig. 5d. The fans maintained low and constant energy consumption
 334 values throughout the day, and small oscillations were found for the HC.

335 Fig. 5. Daily operational characteristics of the DX system for the climatic conditions of
 336 Barcelona.

3.1.2 Daily behaviour of the DW-IEC system

337
338 The results of the daily simulations for the DW-IEC system on a typical winter day and a typical
339 summer day in Barcelona are represented in Fig. 6. Regarding the winter day, the outdoor air
340 humidity was lower than the set point air humidity, see Fig. 6a, so air dehumidification was not
341 necessary and the mode of operation Mode 1-H was activated, deactivating the DW, HC1 and
342 Fan3, see Fig. 3. In this case, the outdoor humidity was the supply humidity. Then, the air process
343 stream was handled by the IEC unit, which was used as a SHE, recovering sensible heat from the
344 return air stream. However, the outlet air temperature of the SHE was lower than the set point
345 temperature, so a post-heating by HC2 was required to increase the air temperature, according to
346 Mode 3-T. As a result of this, the energy consumption of the DW, HC1 and Fan3 were zero, the
347 energy consumption of HC2 varied according to the outdoor air temperature and the PLF values
348 of the heat pump, and the energy consumption of Fan 1 and Fan 3 were constant throughout the
349 day, see Fig. 6b. The highest energy consumption values were those of Fan 1, due to the process
350 side pressure losses.

351 On the summer day analysed, the outdoor air humidity was higher than the set point humidity,
352 see Fig. 6c, so the Mode 2-H control activates the DW and HC1. All simulations were carried out
353 under assumption that the DW is regenerated with air heated to relatively low temperature values
354 (40–60 °C). The outlet process air temperature of the DW was higher than the set point air
355 temperature. Therefore, Mode 1-T was activated and the process air stream was cooled by the
356 IEC, thus achieving the set point air conditions and supplying the air stream to the building. HC1
357 showed the highest energy consumption values for the summer day, due to the regeneration
358 energy required by the DW. The energy consumption of post-heating by HC2 was not required,
359 so this was zero.

360 Fig. 6. Daily operational characteristics of the DW-IEC system for the climatic conditions of

361 Barcelona.

362 It can be observed that the supply air humidity of the DW-IEC system was lower than the supply
 363 air humidity of the DX system, because the process air flow rate of the DW-IEC system was lower
 364 than that of the DX system. Thus, the latent energy delivered to the building with both systems
 365 was similar.

366 These case studies show that the modes of operation set for both systems provided the required
 367 indoor air conditions in the building in every season.

368 **3.2 Monthly energy analysis**

369 A monthly energy analysis for both HVAC systems for the climatic conditions of Barcelona was
370 performed. Monthly sensible and latent energy delivered and monthly energy consumption by the
371 DX and DW-IEC systems were obtained.

372 **3.2.1 Monthly energy analysis of the DX system**

373 The sensible and latent energy delivered of the DX system for the climatic conditions of
374 Barcelona, climate zone 4, are represented in Fig. 7. This figure shows energy delivered of each
375 element and the total monthly energy. The negative energy values indicate that the elements
376 reduced the air temperature and humidity ratio, and the positive energy values indicate that the
377 elements increased the air temperature and humidity ratio. It can be observed that the process of
378 mixing air slightly increased the sensible energy delivered, see Fig. 7a, thus increasing the outlet
379 air temperature of the mixing box. This process caused the sensible energy required by the HC to
380 decrease, especially in January and December, where the sensible energy delivered in the process
381 of mixing air is greater than in the remaining months, 7.2 kWh m⁻² and 7.5 kWh m⁻², respectively.
382 However, the mixing air also increased the latent energy delivered, see Fig. 7b, thus increasing
383 the outlet air humidity of the mixing box. For example, the latent energy values delivered in
384 January and December were 15.2 kWh m⁻² and 16.2 kWh m⁻², respectively. Therefore, the mixing
385 air did not improve the dehumidification system performance for the climate conditions of
386 Barcelona.

387 The EV delivered sensible and latent energy during the months with dehumidification demand,
388 i.e. when the mixed air humidity ratio was higher than the set point air humidity ratio, from April
389 to November. The maximum sensible and latent energy values delivered by the EV were obtained
390 in July and August. The building did not require dehumidification from December to March,
391 therefore, the sensible and latent energy delivered by the EV was zero.

392 The sensible energy delivered by the HC was maintained throughout the year, due to the heating
393 demand, i.e. when the inlet air temperature to the HC was lower than the set point air temperature.

394 This temperature was lower the set point air temperature from November to April, due mainly to
 395 the outdoor air, and from May to October, due to the low outlet air temperature of the EV.
 396 Finally, it can be observed that the annual sensible and latent energy values delivered by the DX
 397 system were 365.7 kWh m⁻² year⁻¹ and -260.2 kWh m⁻² year⁻¹, respectively.

398 Fig. 7. Energy delivered by each element for the DX system for the climatic conditions of
 399 Barcelona, (a) sensible energy delivered and (b) latent energy delivered.

400 The monthly energy consumption of the DX system is represented in Fig. 8. This figure shows
 401 the monthly energy consumption of each element and the total monthly consumption. It can be
 402 observed that the highest energy consumption values were those for the compressor, which was

403 activated during the months with dehumidification demand. The operation Fan3 was linked to
 404 that of the compressor, see Fig. 1, therefore, the energy consumption of Fan3 was zero during the
 405 months that the compressor was not in operation, from December to March. The energy
 406 consumption of the HC was maintained throughout the year, due to its sensible energy demand,
 407 as shown in Fig. 7a. The energy consumption of the HC was that of the heat pump. Regarding the
 408 monthly energy consumption, the maximum values were found from May to October, due mainly
 409 to the high dehumidification demand. The energy consumption was less during cold months with
 410 high heating demand, from November to February, and warm months, such as March and April.
 411 It can also be observed that the annual energy consumption for the climatic conditions of
 412 Barcelona with the DX system was 493.1 kWh m⁻² year⁻¹, see Fig. 8.

413
 414 Fig. 8. Monthly energy consumption of each element for the DX system for the climatic
 415 conditions of Barcelona.

416 3.2.2 Monthly energy analysis of the DW-IEC system

417 The sensible and latent energy delivered of the DW-IEC system for the climatic conditions of
 418 Barcelona is shown in Fig. 9, broken down by the elements. It can be observed that the DW
 419 delivered high latent energy values from April to November, as shown in Fig. 9b, due to the
 420 dehumidification demand. The peak values, corresponding to July and August, are due to the high
 421 outdoor air humidity. The operation of HC1 was linked to that of the DW, in order to regenerate
 422 it, see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The sensible energy of HC1 was not delivered to the building, but outside.

423 The activation of the IEC was caused by the sensible energy delivered during the dehumidification
 424 process of the DW. As a consequence, sensible energy delivered by the IEC is obtained from
 425 April to November, in order to reduce the process air temperature, see Fig. 9a. The SHE recovered
 426 a large amount of energy during the months with heating demand and the DW was not in
 427 operation, thus reducing the energy required by HC2. The highest sensible energy values
 428 delivered by HC2 was found during the months with high heating demand, from November to
 429 March, months with low outdoor temperatures. Nevertheless, the sensible energy delivered by
 430 HC2 was zero from June to September, as shown in Fig. 9a.

431 Fig. 9. Energy delivered by each element for the DW-IEC system for the climatic conditions of
 432 Barcelona, (a) sensible energy delivered and (b) latent energy delivered.

433 Finally, comparing these results with those obtained with the DX system, it can be observed that
434 the monthly sensible and latent energy delivered to the building by each system was similar, see
435 Fig. 7 and Fig. 9. The slight variations in the energy values delivered between both systems were
436 mainly due to the different control systems used.

437 The monthly energy consumption by each element of the DW-IEC system are shown in Fig. 10.
438 It can be observed that the element with the highest energy consumption values throughout the
439 year was Fan1, 119.1 kWh m^{-2} , due to the high pressure drop of the proposed system. High energy
440 consumption values by HC1 were found during the months with high dehumidification demand,
441 from April to November. However, very low dehumidification demand was obtained from
442 December to March, so the monthly energy consumption values by HC1 were very low or zero,
443 see Fig. 10. The energy consumption of HC1 and HC2 were those of the heat pump. It can also
444 be observed that the trend of energy consumption by HC2 was contrary to that of HC1. The
445 highest energy consumption values by HC2 were found November to April, due to the heating
446 demand, and the lowest values from May to October, because the outlet process air temperature
447 of the DW was usually higher than the set point air temperature. The energy consumption of Fan3
448 was very low during the months that the DW was not in operation, since the operation of Fan2
449 was linked to that of the DW, see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The maximum monthly energy consumption
450 values were found from May to October, due mainly to the high dehumidification demand, and
451 then, as with the DX system. Finally, the annual energy consumption for the climatic conditions
452 of Barcelona with the proposed DW-IEC system was $314.7 \text{ kWh m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$, as shown in Fig. 10.
453 Therefore, the annual energy consumption of the DW-IEC system was 36.2 % lower than that of
454 the DX system for the climatic conditions of Barcelona, see Fig. 8 and Fig. 10.

455

456 Fig. 10. Monthly energy consumption for the DW-IEC system for the climatic conditions of

457

Barcelona.

458

3.3 Annual energy analysis

459

In this section, the annual energy consumption of the proposed DW-IEC system was compared

460

with those of the DX system. The comparative analysis was carried out for the 6 climate zones,

461

as shown in Table 9.

462

3.3.1 Annual energy consumption

463

The operating annual energy consumption of both systems for the 6 climate zones is shown in

464

Fig. 11. It can be observed that the maximum annual consumption values for both systems were

465

obtained for the climate zone 1, a very hot climate zone, due to the high dehumidification demand.

466

The energy consumption values were significantly reduced for cool climatic conditions, such as

467

in climate zone 5. The consumption decreased by 51 % and 37 % between the climate zone 1 and

468

5 for the DX system and the DW-IEC system, respectively. However, the annual energy

469

consumption values increased for climate zone 6, a cold climate zone, compared to those of zones

470

3, 4 and 5. This increase was caused mainly by the high heating demand. This trend of annual

471

energy consumption was also obtained for the monthly energy consumption analysed in section

472

3.2, where the highest monthly consumption values were found for the months with high

473 dehumidification demand, then, the months with high heating demand and finally, the remaining
 474 months.

475 It can be observed that the annual energy consumption of the DW-IEC system was always lower
 476 than that of the DX system, obtaining significant energy savings, always over 27.8 %, see Fig.
 477 11. The highest energy savings were found for the climate zones with the highest annual energy
 478 consumption and the highest dehumidification demand, zones 1 and 2, with 43.5 % and 46.8 %,
 479 respectively.

480
 481 Fig. 11. Comparative analysis of annual energy consumption of the DW-IEC system and the
 482 DX system in each climate zone.

483 3.3.2 Seasonal mean coefficient of performance

484 The seasonal mean coefficient of performance, SCOP, of both systems, was calculated using Eq.
 485 (8). The SCOP values for the 6 climate zones are represented in Fig. 12. It can be observed that
 486 the maximum SCOP value for the DX system was 1.9, obtained from a cool climate zone, zone
 487 5. Nevertheless, the maximum SCOP value for the DW-IEC system was 2.8, obtained from a very
 488 hot climate zone, zone 1.

489 The SCOP values of the DW-IEC system were always higher than that of the DX system, always
 490 over 27 %, as shown in Fig. 12. The greatest differences in SCOP between both systems, Δ SCOP,
 491 were found for climate zones 1 and 2, and the lowest for climate zones 5 and 6. The trend of

492 Δ SCOP was similar to the trend of annual energy saving, as shown in Fig. 11, since the sensible
 493 and latent energy delivered to the building by each system were the same, so Δ SCOP depended
 494 exclusively on energy consumption.

495
 496 Fig. 12. SCOP values of the DW-IEC system and the DX system in each climate zone.

497 3.3.3 Energy consumption per unit of dehumidified water

498 The energy consumption per unit of dehumidified water, E_{cons} , was obtained for both system, in
 499 order to know the energy used only when the dehumidification demand was required. The E_{cons}
 500 results for each system and climate zone, are shown in Fig. 13. It can be observed that the lowest
 501 E_{cons} values were obtained for very hot climatic conditions, such as in climate zone 1 and the
 502 highest E_{cons} values for cool conditions, such as in climate zone 5. The trend of E_{cons} is contrary
 503 to that obtained for annual energy consumption, see Fig. 11. Comparing both systems studied, it
 504 can be observed that the E_{cons} values from the DX system were always higher than those from the
 505 DW-IEC system. The highest energy saving, ΔE_{cons} , was obtained for zone 1, 34.6 %. However,
 506 small energy savings were found for zones 5 and 6, 4.4 % and 1.7 %, respectively, climate zones
 507 with low dehumidification demand.

508

509 Fig. 13. E_{cons} values of the DW-IEC system and the DX system in each climate zone.

510 4 Conclusions

511 In the present work, the energy potential and desiccant capacity of two air handling systems were
 512 analysed. The first system was composed mainly of a DW and an IEC, DW-IEC system, and the
 513 second system of a direct expansion conventional unit, DX system. Several detailed energy
 514 simulations were carried out with the assumption that both systems served a spa room. 6 different
 515 climatic conditions, from very hot zones to cold zones, were used to performed the simulations.

516 The results showed that the systems satisfactorily achieved the set point air conditions. Both
 517 systems delivered similar sensible and latent energy values to the building. The IEC system
 518 reduced the high air temperatures generated by the adsorption process of the DW.

519 The annual energy consumption of the DW-IEC system was lower than that of the DX system for
 520 the 6 climate zones, achieving significant energy savings, especially for hot climate zones with
 521 high dehumidification demand, where a 46.8 % annual energy saving was obtained. The lowest
 522 energy saving was achieved for a cool climate zone, 27.8 %. These energy savings resulted in
 523 better SCOP values for the DW-IEC system. The highest SCOP value was 2.8, obtained for a very
 524 hot climatic zone. The difference in SCOP between both systems was always greater than 25%
 525 for all climate zones.

526 Finally, the energy consumption per unit of dehumidified water, E_{cons} , of both systems was
527 analysed for the 6 climate zones. Significant energy savings were obtained with the proposed
528 DW-IEC system for very hot climate zone, due to the high dehumidification demand, achieving
529 up to 34.6% savings. However, the energy savings of the DW-IEC system were lower for cool
530 and cold climate zones, 4.4 % and 1.7 %, respectively, climate zones with low dehumidification
531 demand and high heating demand.

532 The results suggest that the proposed system with a DW and an IEC could be a serious alternative
533 to the DX systems composed of direct expansion units, to handle air in small buildings with high
534 latent loads and low supply air flow rates, such as spas.

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